

Australian Research Data Commons

NCRIS Program Guidelines

Program: FAIR Data and Secure Access

Purpose

These guidelines provide project partners with the strategy, outcomes, and expectations for projects under the NCRIS FAIR and Secure Access program. They outline how projects will contribute to the development of national-scale infrastructure that enables researchers to securely discover, access, and reuse health and medical data in alignment with FAIR principles.

Program Overview

The FAIR and Secure Access Program is part of the Australian Research Data Commons' (ARDC) People Research Data Commons. Its goal is to strengthen national research capabilities by improving the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of data while ensuring that access is secure, ethical, and appropriately governed.

Researchers, health services, governments and industry face challenges in working with distributed data. These include difficulties in discovering datasets, inconsistent metadata and standards, and complex approval processes for accessing sensitive information. By addressing these issues, the program will provide a coordinated foundation that supports high-quality, responsible research at scale.

The program works in close collaboration with national research infrastructure facilities, including those funded under NCRIS, as well as research organisations, government, and industry. By supporting these facilities, the program ensures that data assets and services are aligned, sustainable, and embedded within the broader national research infrastructure ecosystem.

Program Outcomes

The program will deliver value through:

- Trusted, secure infrastructure for managing and accessing sensitive data.
- Standardised metadata and discovery systems that make datasets FAIR and reusable.
- Clear governance frameworks that align with national standards, ethical guidelines, and sovereignty principles.
- Integration and interoperability with existing national and international infrastructures.
- Partnerships across NCRIS facilities, research organisations, and government that ensure solutions are sustainable and scalable.

Project Requirements

Projects must:

- Address significant challenges in FAIR data or secure access for health and medical research.
- Develop or enhance national-scale, integrated infrastructure that is enduring and sustained beyond the project.
- Align with existing NCRIS capabilities, standards, and frameworks.
- Use and contribute to community-agreed persistent identifiers, vocabularies, and metadata standards.
- Document data integration processes to support reproducibility and future projects.
- Be co-designed with either partners, researchers, government, industry, and community stakeholders.
- Actively share outputs and learnings across ARDC and NCRIS programs.

In Scope

Projects may include:

- Establishing or enhancing metadata registries and discovery platforms.
- Implementing secure access frameworks and data spaces.
- Developing API-based systems for syndication and integration of metadata.
- Building governance, policy, and participation frameworks for secure data access.
- Defining and applying standards for sensitive data management.

Out of Scope

ARDC cannot invest directly in:

- Research activities primarily focused on hypothesis testing, discovery science, or clinical experimentation, where the primary output is new scientific knowledge rather than infrastructure.
- Collection of new data solely for research purposes (e.g., new surveys, clinical sampling, experimental trials).

However, ARDC investment may support:

- Generation of reference datasets or workflows where these are necessary to establish national-scale infrastructure (e.g. curated registries, pipelines, baseline multi-omic datasets etc), provided the outputs are enduring, standardised, and FAIR-aligned.

Investment and Duration

- ARDC will provide investment under NCRIS with a minimum 1:1 co-investment requirement (cash and/or in-kind).
- Projects are not expected to run for more than 2 years.
- Outputs must be sustainable beyond the project's lifetime, with clear custodianship and maintenance plans.

ARDC Expectations for Co-Investment Projects

All projects supported under the NCRIS FAIR and Secure Access Program are required to meet ARDC's expectations for co-investment projects. Specifically:

- Co-investment ratio: Partners must provide a minimum 1:1 co-investment (cash and/or in-kind), documented in an auditable form. See the [ARDC Co-Investment Guidelines](#) for details.
- Alignment with national frameworks: Projects must align with the NCRIS 2023 Guidelines and principles set out in the NRI Roadmap.

- Dedicated project management: Each project must have a project manager provided by the partner organisation, with appropriate experience and capacity to manage delivery. ARDC will not provide direct project management. Depending on project needs, ARDC may also require a named technical lead and/or research lead.
- Governance structures: Projects must establish ARDC-approved governance arrangements, which may include a program-wide steering committee and/or user reference groups, with defined Terms of Reference.
- Progress reporting: Monthly traffic-light progress reports are required, with tracking of KPIs, adoption metrics, and translation impacts.
- Post-project and ongoing success monitoring: ARDC and the project will agree on shared success metrics. The project must establish mechanisms to track ongoing outcomes for long-term reporting, including user numbers, research outputs, dataset records, data requests, impact stories and use cases.
- Financial reporting: Projects must provide annual financial acquittal reports at agreed intervals and on project completion. These reports must account for both ARDC investment and partner co-investment, in accordance with [ARDC's Co-Investment Guidelines](#).
- Sustainability: Outputs must include a plan for ongoing maintenance and custodianship beyond the project life to ensure enduring national benefit.
- FAIR outputs: Project outputs (including software and infrastructure) should be made as FAIR as possible, supporting reuse, reproducibility, and interoperability.
- Collaboration: Project teams are expected to collaborate with other ARDC and NCRIS initiatives, share knowledge and outputs where relevant, and contribute to cross-program goals.
- Engagement and communication: Project teams are responsible for planning communication and engagement activities for their project. These activities should be planned and delivered in collaboration with partners and ARDC's Communications team to provide input and support where needed. All public outputs should acknowledge ARDC and NCRIS.